

Vanadium. Part XV. Oxo-Vanadium(IV) and Oxo-Vanadium(V) Complexes of some Organic Ligands

R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal

A number of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of acetoacetanilides, kojic acid, salicylamidoxime and nitroso-naphthols are described. The complexes are all paramagnetic (1.6-1.9 B.M.) The reflectance spectra of the turquoise green bis kojato oxo-vanadium (IV) shows three absorption bands with the suggestion of a shoulder in the longest wave length region. I. R. spectra of a few complexes are also reported.

A few oxo-vanadium (V) complexes are also described. These are as usual diamagnetic.

During the last few years, considerable interest has been shown in vanadium chemistry, especially with oxo-vanadium(IV).¹⁻¹⁰ Of the various organic ligands that have been investigated, acetylacetone and other β -diketones have received major attention from the standpoint of preparation¹¹, adduct formation¹², formation constant¹³, magnetic and spectral studies¹⁴. Though the oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes with β -diketones are well

1. Selbin, *Chem. Revs.*, 1965, 65, 153.
2. Dutta and Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 1001; 1962, 39, 871, 860; 1963, 40, 53, 67, 857; 1964, 41, 62, 546.
3. Dutta and Ghosh, *this Journal*, Parts IX—XIV and also *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 247
4. Carlin and Walker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 2128.
5. Selbin and Morpurgo, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 673.
6. Ramaiah and Martin, *ibid*, 1965, 27, 1663.
7. Fowles *et. al*, *ibid*, 1965, 27, 1999.
8. Paul and Kumar, *ibid*, 1965, 27, 2587.
9. Garvey and Ragdale, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1604.
10. Horner, Tyrce and Vencaky, *ibid*, 1962, 1, 844.
11. (a) Morgan and Moss, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 78.
(b) Rosenheim and Mong, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 148, 25.
(c) Jones, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 76, 5995.
12. Claunch, Martin and Jones, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1073.
13. Trujillo and Brito, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, 50, 15320.
14. Selbin *et. al*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 1315.

established, nothing has so far appeared in the literature concerning substituted acetoacetanilides and closely related kojic acid.

The substituted acetoacetanilides are capable of keto-enol tautomerism. The acid dissociation constants show that acetoacetanilides are stronger bases than acetylacetone.¹⁵ Little work has been reported concerning the complexing ability of these acetoacetanilides. A report on the formation constant of the beryllium complex¹⁵ along with its use in the gravimetric estimation of the same metal^{16a} and a photometric evaluation of the composition and the instability constant of a Fe (III) complex^{16b} are all that has appeared so far. We have studied the oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of the ligands, acetoacetanilide, acetoacet-*o*-toluidide, acetoacet-*o*-anisidide and acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide (BH). With all these ligands, light green to bluish green crystalline products have been isolated by operating in aqueous alcohol medium. These conform to the composition of $[VOR_n] \cdot X \cdot H_2O$. The water mostly stays outside the coordination zone as evident from its ready loss at 110-120° with no colour change accompanying dehydration. Our attempts to obtain pyridine or similar other adducts did not quite materialise. The complexes are all paramagnetic, giving effective magnetic moments of 1.62-1.93 B.M. This is what has been observed in all quadrivalent vanadium complexes of 3d¹ system in our Laboratory and also elsewhere. The complexes, being insoluble in all common solvents we could not get the electronic absorption spectra in solution. The infrared spectra of the complexes reveal, as for the oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes strong vanadyl band¹⁷ around 980cm⁻¹. The corresponding band in acetylacetonato oxo-vanadium (IV) is located at 996 cm⁻¹.

TABLE I

Magnetic measurements

Temp. = 31° C

Compounds	Dia. (corr.) × 10 ⁶	λ_m (corr.) × 10 ⁶	μ_{eff} (B.M.) ^a
1. [VO (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂]	187	1495	1.90
2. [VO (C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ N) ₂] H ₂ O	200	1506	1.93
3. [VO (C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ N) ₂] H ₂ O	208	1085	1.62
4. [VO (C ₆ H ₅ O ₄) ₂]	122	1956	1.61
5. [VO (C ₇ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂) ₂]	150	1056	1.61
6. [VO (OH) (C ₇ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂) ₂] 2H ₂ O			Diamagnetic
7. [VO (C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	192	1506	1.93
8. [VO (C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	192	1397	1.86
9. [VO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ N)]			Diamagnetic

^a Calculated from λ_m (corr.) using Curie equation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (\lambda_m \text{ (corr.) } T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

C₁₀H₁₂O₂N = acetoacetanilide; C₁₁H₁₂O₂N = acetoacet-*o*-toluidide; C₁₀H₁₂O₂N = acetoacet-*o*-anisidide; C₆H₅O₄ = kojic acid; C₇H₇O₂N₂ = salicylamidoxime; C₁₀H₇O₂N = α -nitroso- β -naphthol or β -nitroso- α -naphthol. Compound 7 and 9 are α -nitroso- β -naphthol complexes and compound 8 is β -nitroso- α -naphthol complex.

15. Harris et al., *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 519.

16. (a) Das and Banerjee, *Z. anal. Chem.* 1961, 184, 110.

(b) Korkuc and Lipiec, *Chem. Abstr.*, 61, 4935 g.

17. Selbin, Holmes and McGlynn, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 1359.

Kojic acid forms a five membered chelate ring with hydrogen or a metal ion, which is the same as tropolone. Investigations have been carried out on the formation constants

of many metal ion complexes of this ligand. Kojic acid as β -diketone was found to form complexes whose stabilities were nearly equal to the corresponding metal chelates of β -diketones of the same acidity in aqueous media^{18a,b}. In this light, we have synthesized the deep turquoise green complex $[\text{VO}(\text{Kojate})_2]$, which has no aqua molecule inside the coordination zone. The sample is paramagnetic with a moment value of 1.61 B.M. responding to the requirement of one unpaired electron in the system. A 0.001M aqueous solution provides $\Lambda M = 10$ mhos (at 30°C), indicating the non electrolyte nature of the complex. The infrared spectra reveals a strong vanadyl band at 990 cm^{-1} , which is close to what pertains in $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$. The diffuse reflectance spectra (Fig.1) provides three absorption bands in the visible range at $380 \text{ m}\mu$ ($26,312 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at $570 \text{ m}\mu$ ($17,543 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and at $682 \text{ m}\mu$ ($14,662 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The complex $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ in a C_{4v} symmetry provides, accord-

Fig. 1. Diffuse reflectance spectra of $[\text{VO}(\text{Kojate})_2]$

ing to Ballhausen and Gray model^{18a} three electronic absorption bands representing the transitions $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$ & d_{xz} ; $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$; $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$. In complexes of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$ or $[\text{VO}(\text{Kojate})_2]$ with a C_{2v} symmetry four crystal field bands may be expected¹⁴. However our system provides three bands and the suggestion of a shoulder beyond the long wavelength peak. Low temperature reflectance spectra might have revealed more about the further splitting of this shoulder as has been observed in $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$ system¹⁴. The complex dissolves in water to form a greenish yellow solution, which under the limitation of the solubility, did not provide any bands in the longer wave length regions. The sample also slowly dissolves in alcohol to form a pale orange solution and on refluxing provided an orange colour. These observations, in our judgement, stand for oxidation of the

18. (a) Bryant and Fernelius, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 5351.

(b) Murakami, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1962, 35, 52, 679.

complex to presumably a vanadium (V) species. However, in solid crystalline state, this is perfectly stable to air oxidation. It was probably this tendency towards oxidation which prevented isolation of any pure product with any other donor ligands. The complex *bis*-acetylacetonate oxo-vanadium (IV), to which the present kojate complex has some relations, was also found to change its original bluish green hue in 2 : 1 : 1 ether: toluene: ethanol solvent over hours and days to yellow. This was followed spectrophotometrically and it was discovered that the d-d-ligand field bands in the long wave length ranges of 3d¹ oxo-vanadium (IV) were ultimately missing; the only one remaining was the one, to which a charge transfer origin might reasonably be ascribed^{19b}. In our kojate system, the oxidation is even faster.

We have next investigated the syntheses and properties of oxo-vanadium (V) complexes of salicylamidoxime. This work was prompted by a very keen interest shown on the oxo-vanadium (V) complexes of salicylaldoxime by a number of research groups²⁰⁻²², the Japanese group apparently being unaware of the good amount of work already done in this context. Since, it was shown that salicylamidoxime was extremely close in its properties to salicylaldoxime²², we thought it worthwhile to extend the area of vanadium complexes to salicylamidoxime. The ligand reacts with vanadyl sulphate in a hydrogen atmosphere to produce a voluminous ash coloured product, which is somewhat stable in a dry atmosphere but readily undergoes oxidation in moist condition to vanadium (V). The magnetic moment, when freshly prepared and dried, is 1.6 B.M. showing the presence of a single unpaired electron. Ammonium vanadate reacts in a aqueous medium around pH 3 to furnish a dark greenish black product, identified as oxo-hydroxo *bis*-salicylamidoximate-vanadium (V). This on refluxing with ethanol dissolves to give a red solution, from which ethoxo derivative was obtained. The reaction with vanadium (V) was earlier observed qualitatively²³. Our observations further extends the vista of similarities of the two reagents, salicylaldoxime and salicylamidoxime.

α -Nitroso- β -naphthol has long been reported as a reagent for semimicro detection of vanadium (V)²⁴. We have studied this reaction elaborately under a variety of conditions. The composition of the bright red crystalline precipitate was found to be variable and ultimately we succeeded in finding out the requisites to have a pure product [VO₂R], (where R₂H = a molecule of the ligand). A paramagnetic oxo-vanadium (IV) complex has also been characterised. Similar studies have been completed with β -nitroso- α -naphthol with similar results.

In general, complexes reported in this communication were not soluble in any organic solvent, so as to permit any evaluation of the molecular size.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -Nitroso- α -naphthol was prepared according to the method described elsewhere²⁵. Salicylamidoxime was prepared according to the published procedure²². Vanadyl sulphate

19. (a) Ballhausen and Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 111.

(b) Ortolano, Selbin and McGlynn, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 41, 262.

20. Beilig and Mollinger, *Annalen*, 1957, 605, 117.

21. Nakamura, Shimura and Tsuchida, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1963, 36, 296.

22. Dondrio, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, 14163b.

23. Bandyopadhyay and Ray, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 21, 65.

24. Shchynakin and Bolokon, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1938, 32, 4467.

25. Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", D. Van Nostrand Company, Vol-III, p.321.

pentahydrate was a B.D.H. product. The other ligands were all B.D.H. L.R. variety and used directly.

bis-Aceto-acetanilido-oxo-vanadium (IV) — Acetoacetanilide (0.36 g), dissolved in methanol (10 ml), was treated under stirring with an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g. in 5 ml.). pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.5 by dil. ammonium hydroxide, when light bluish green crystals separated. These were filtered, washed first with water and then with methanol and dried in air. The compound was insoluble in water, alcohol, acetone and benzene. [Found: V, 12.4; N, 6.9. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$ requires V, 12.1; N, 6.6%.]

bis-Acet-o-acet-o-toluidido-oxo-vanadium (IV) *Monohydrate*. — It was prepared as green crystals by following the above procedure using aceto-aceto-toluidide (0.39 g) instead of acetoacetanilide. The substance was insoluble in water, alcohol and benzene. [Found: V, 10.8; N, 5.8; H_2O (by loss at 110°C), 3.5 $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$ H_2O requires V, 10.9; N, 6.0; H_2O , 3.8%.]

bis-Acet-o-acet-o-anisidido-oxo-vanadium (IV) *Monohydrate*. — Aceto-aceto-anisidide (0.42 g), dissolved in ethanol (10 ml), was treated under stirring with an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g in 5 ml.), when an oil separated. This was washed and scratched with ethanol and kept overnight at room temperature. The oil solidified to olive green crystals. These were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 . [Found: V, 10.0; N, 5.3; H_2O (by loss at 110°C), 3.0. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$ H_2O requires V, 10.2; N, 5.6; H_2O , 3.6%.]

bis-Aceto-acet-o-chloro-anilido-oxo-vanadium (IV). It was obtained as green crystals by following a similar procedure as above using aceto-acet-o-chloro-anilide (0.43 g). [Found: V, 10.2; N, 5.4. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{NCl})_2]$ requires V, 10.4; N, 5.7%.]

bis-Kojato-oxo-vanadium (IV). — Kojic acid (0.30 g), dissolved in water (5 ml), was treated under stirring with an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g in 5 ml). pH of the bluish green solution was adjusted to 4 with dilute NaOH and the resulting solution was concentrated on a water bath and then allowed to cool. Deep turquoise green crystals separated and were filtered, washed with ice cold water and dried in air. The substance is soluble in water and alcohol and insoluble in benzene. The compound suffers no loss of weight at 120° . [Found V, 14.4; C, 40.4; H, 2.8. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_4)_2]$ requires V, 14.5; C, 41.2; H, 2.8%.] The alcoholic solution is yellow to red depending on the concentration of the complex.

bis-Salicylamidoximato-oxo-vanadium (IV). — Salicylamidoxime (0.45 g), dissolved in water (5 ml) saturated with hydrogen, was treated under stirring with an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g in 5 ml) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. A voluminous ash coloured precipitate was formed, which was filtered in hydrogen atmosphere, washed with water saturated with hydrogen and dried in vacuo over CaCl_2 . It is readily oxidised to the pentavalent state by atmospheric oxygen. [Found: V, 13.5; N, 15.0. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)_2]$ requires V, 13.8; N, 15.1%.]

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-Salicylamidoximato vanadium (V) *Dihydrate*. — Salicylamidoxime (0.45 g), dissolved in water (5 ml), was treated with an aqueous solution of $\text{NH}_4\text{VO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

(0.13 g in 5 ml). An intense greenish black solution was obtained. pH of the solution was adjusted to 3 by dil. H_2SO_4 , when a greenish black precipitate was formed, which was filtered, washed with water and dried in air. The substance is insoluble in water and chloroform. It is soluble in acetone, alcohol, isoamyl alcohol giving a red violet solution. [Found: V, 12.2; N, 13.30; H_2O (by loss at $110^\circ C$), 8.0. $[VO(OH)(C_7H_7O_2N_2)] \cdot 2 H_2O$ requires V, 12.0; N, 13.27; H_2O , 8.5%]

Oxo-ethoxy-bis-Salicylamidooximate-vanadium (V).—The greenish black compound (0.5 g) as prepared above was refluxed with ethanol (15 ml) for 2 hr. to produce a yellow solution. The solution was then allowed to evaporate at room temperature. The yellow crystals separated were filtered and dried in air. [Found: V, 12.2; N, 13.4. $[VO(OC_2H_5)(C_7H_7O_2N_2)]$ requires V, 12.3; N, 13.5%].

bis- α -Nitroso- β -naphtholato-oxo-vanadium (IV).— α -Nitroso- β -naphthol (0.35 g), dissolved in hot ethanol (5 ml), was treated with an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g in 5 ml). pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.5 with dil. NH_4OH . A black voluminous precipitate was formed, which was filtered, washed with water and dried in air. [Found: V, 12.6; N, 7.1. $[VO(C_{10}H_6O_2N)_2]$ requires V, 12.4; N, 6.8%].

Dioxo- α -nitroso- β -naphtholato-vanadium (V)— α -Nitroso- β -naphthol (0.26 g), dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid, was treated with an aqueous solution of $NaVO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$ (0.20 g in 10 ml). A brownish red precipitate appeared. This was diluted with five to six times of water and digested on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. This was then decanted and digested with ethanol. The dark red precipitate formed was filtered hot, washed first with hot water and then with hot ethanol and dried in air. [Found: V, 19.9; N, 5.8. $[VO_2(C_{10}H_6O_2N)]$ requires V, 19.9; N, 5.5%].

bis- β -Nitroso- α -naphtholato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—It was prepared by following a similar procedure as for the α -nitroso- β -naphthol derivative. The compound is black in colour. [Found: V, 12.5; N, 7.0. $[VO(C_{10}H_6O_2N)_2]$ requires V, 12.4; N, 6.8%].

Dioxo- β -Nitroso- α -naphtholato vanadium (V).—It was obtained as chocolate red precipitate by following a similar procedure as for the α -nitroso- β -naphthol compound [Found: V, 20.2; N, 5.3. $[VO_2(C_{10}H_6O_2N)]$ requires V, 19.9; N, 5.5%].

General Experimental Procedure—Vanadium was estimated gravimetrically as pentoxide after igniting the complexes to a constant weight. Nitrogen was determined by the semimicro combustion technique. Magnetic susceptibility was found out by Gouy method using recrystallised copper sulphate pentahydrate as the calibrant and using a field strength of about 9.20×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic correction of the ligands was applied by the use of Pascal's constants²⁵.

We wish to express our gratitude to Prof. J. N. Chatterjee of Patna University for the carbon and hydrogen analysis and to Prof. G.W.A. Fowles of Reading University, for the diffuse reflectance spectra.

We wish also to record our thanks to the C.S.I.R. for financial assistance to one of us (A.S.) and to Prof. S.R. Palit and Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for their interest in our programme. We also desire to express our gratitude to Mr. N. N. Ghosh of the University College of Science, Calcutta for allowing us to work with the Magnetic Balance.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
BURDWAN, WEST BENGAL.

Received May 16, 1966

Corrigendum;—vol. 44 No. 4, p. 341, 1967, Fig. 9, Read "From *below*" in place of "From *above*"